

Piṅgalāmata chapter 6, verses 1-107b, edition

A f46v, line 1; B38v, line 6; C f22v, line 12.

piṅgalovāca

6.1 tac ca prāsādagaṃ deva sūcitaṃ na prakāśitam
bhūparigrahapūrvam ca prāsādānāṃ ca lakṣaṇam

6.2ab kathayasva prasādena kālakāmāndhakāntaka

bhairava uvāca

6.2cd mānonmānapramāṇaṃ ca bhūparigrahapūrvakam

6.3 prāsādalakṣaṇaṃ vakṣye śṛṇuṣvekāgramānasā
tatra bhūmivibhāgaṃ tu samyag ādau vilakṣayet

C f23r

6.4 puṇyaṃ kṣetropakṣetraṃ ca saṃdohaṃ pīṭham eva vā
upapīṭhopasaṃdohe nadyobhayataṭe 'pi vā

B f39r

6.5 nagāgre tv abdhītire vā nagare grāmakhetake
ekavṛkṣe śmaśāne vā nadīnāṃ saṃgameṣu ca

6.6 tricatuhpañcaśṛṅgāṭe kuhare gahvare tathā
kāmike vā svadigbhāge tatra bhūmiṃ parīkṣayet

Ω = AB(→C)

piṅgalovāca] BC; piṅgala uvāca A

1a prāsādagaṃ] A; prasādagaṃ BC 3a vakṣye] AC; vakṣe B

3b ekāgra AB; aikāgra C • mānasā] A; mānas[[aḥ]]{ā} B; mānasāḥ C

4a puṇyaṃ] A; puṇya BC • kṣetropakṣetraṃ] AC; kṣe[[kṣe]]tropakṣetraṃ B

5a nagāgre] AB; nagrāgre C • abdhītire vā] A; abdhirevā[-] C; abdhirevā B

5d nadīnāṃ] AC; nadīnā B

6d bhūmiṃ] AC; bhūmi B • parīkṣayet] BC; parikṣayet A

- 6.7 sitā raktā tathā pītā kṛṣṇābhā brāhmaṇāditaḥ
svā dair vā madhurāmlā ca kaṭukā tiktatā tathā
- 6.8 ghṛtāsṛṇmūtraviṣṭhāntā gandhaiḥ pratyekalakṣitāḥ
brāhmaṇī kuśaroheṇa śararoheṇa kṣatriṇī
- 6.9 vaiśyā dūrvāpraroheṇa kāśaroheṇa śūdrīṇī
soṣarāṃ ca savalmīkāṃ jalākīrṇāṃ vivarjayet
- 6.10 maśakadaṃśakākīrṇāṃ krūrajantvasthisamcayām
kṛṣṇāsmāṅgārasikatākīlakarparavarjitā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

7a pītā] BC; [[pā]]pītā A

8c brāhmaṇī] A; brahmāṇī BC

9b kāśa] em.; kāśa AB; kāśa C

10b samcayām] A; samcayā BC

10c kṛṣṇāsmāṅgāra] A; kṛṣṇāsmāṅgāra BC

8a ghṛtāsṛṇ] em; ghṛtāsṛk ABC

8d kṣatriṇī] A; [-]triṇī C; [-]triṇī B

9c savalmīkāṃ] A; savalmīkāṃ BC

- 6.11 śubhārthe tu śubhā grāhyā aśubhārthe cāśubhā matā
hastamātraṃ khanitvā pāṃsunā pūrayet punaḥ
- 6.12 adhikenottamā bhūmis tatsamena tu madhyamā A f47r
nyūnena kanyasā proktā tridhā bhūmiṃ vilakṣayet
- 6.13 uttame uttamā siddhir madhyame madhyamā bhavet
kanyase kanyasā siddhir māraṇocāṭanādikā
- 6.14 halena tu sulāṅgalyā tricatuḥpañcadhā priye
upariṣṭād vāpayed dhānyāṃs tilān vṛihiyavādikān
- 6.15 caṇakāś caṇakī caiva mudgamāśātasī tathā
godhūmāś caiva nīvārāḥ sarvā hy ekatamāthavā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

11c mātraṃ] AC; mātra B

13a uttame uttamā] A; uttamaṃuttamā C; uttamenaüttameümā B

• siddhir] C; siddhiḥ AB 13c siddhir] BC; siddhi A

13d māraṇocāṭanādikā] BC; māraṇocāṭanādikā A

14a halena] AB; phalena C

• sulaṅgalyā] em.; sulaṅgalya B; sulaṅgalye C; sulaṅgasālya A

14c vāpayed] A; vārayed BC 14d yavādikān] BC; yavādikā A

15a caṇakāś] A; caṇakāṃ BC • caṇakī] A; caṇakīś B; caṇakīṃ C

15c godhūmāś] A; godhūmāś BC

- 6.16 divasatrayaroheṇa uttamā sā prakīrtitā
madhyamā pañcaroheṇa saptaroheṇa kanyasā
- 6.17 tasmād ūrdhvā 'śubhā jñeyā yasmāt sā na prarohiṇī
kaṭakāveṣṭitaṃ kṛtvā tat sthānaṃ tu niśāmukhe
- 6.18 āmakumbhopariṣṭāt tu ghṛtapūrṇāmapātrakam
caturdikṣu caturdīpaṃ dvijādijātivartikam
- 6.19 pūrveṇa brāhmaṇī vartis tāṃ vaktreṇābhimantrayet
dakṣiṇe kṣatriṇī jñeyāghoramantrābhimantritā
- 6.20 paścime śūdrīṇī proktā sadyamantrābhimantritā
uttare vaiśyanī jñeyā vāmadevābhimantritā

B f39v

Ω = AB(→C)

16b prakīrtitā] BC; prakīrtitāḥ A

17b prarohiṇī] AC; prarohaṇī B

17c kaṭakāveṣṭitaṃ] AC; kāṭakāveṣṭitaṃ B

18a kumbhopariṣṭāt] BC; kumbhopariṣṭām A

18c dīpaṃ] BC; dvīpaṃ A

18d vartikam] conj. Sanderson; varttitāṃ AB; varṇitam C

19a vartis] BC; varttiḥ A

19b vaktreṇābhimantrayet] BC; vaktreṇābhisaṃtrayet A

19d mantrābhimantritā] A; mantrābhimantritām BC

20a paścime] BC; paṃcame A

20b sadya] AB; sadye C • mantrābhimantritā] A; mantrābhimantritām BC

- 6.21 svatantravaktramantrair vā praṇavenāthavā priye
sugupte sunirvāte tu astramantrābhirakṣite
- 6.22 diśāvalokanaṃ kṛtvā kavacenāvaguṇṭhayet
prajvalanti yadi sarvāḥ sarveṣāṃ tu hitāvahāḥ
- 6.23 asaṃkīrṇaḥ smṛto vāstuḥ sarvakāmaprasiddhaye
yopaśāntāśubhā tasya śubho 'nyasya viparyaye
- 6.24 sarvaśāntā na śubhāsau punaḥ prajvālītā api
yāvat snehaṃ parīkṣeyyaṃ tad vinā ca na doṣabhāk
- 6.25 evaṃ niśāntam āyātaṃ bhūparigraham ācaret
tatkāle śakunaṃ divyaṃ velodayavilakṣaṇam

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

21a svatantra] AB; svamṭatra C

21b praṇavenāthavā] A; [– –]praṇāthavā C; praṇ[– –]āthavā B

23a asaṃkīrṇaḥ] B; asaṃkīrṇa A; asaṃkīrṇaṃ C

• smṛto] AC; smato B • vāstuḥ] C; vāstu AB

23c yopaśāntāśubhā] em.; yopaśāntāśubhās BC; yopaśāntā'śubhās A

23d viparyaye] BC; viparye A 24a śāntā] AB; śāntīr C

24d vinā ca na] B; vinānaca C; vinānācana A

25a āyātaṃ] BC; ātraiyātaṃ A 25d velodaya] AC; veledaya B

- 6.26 rohiṇyārdrādhaniṣṭhā ca śatabhiṣottaratrayaḥ
śravaṇo maitrasaṃyukto nakṣatrordhvamukhāḥ smṛtāḥ
- 6.27 sthirārambhāḥ praśasyante prāguktatithivārayoḥ
yogas tu karaṇaṃ caiva tārā caiva vipāścite
- 6.28 kiṃtu candraṃ pravakṣyāmi yasmāc candrabalaṃ balam
janmacandras tṛtīyas tu ṣaṣṭho vai saptamaṃ tathā
- 6.29 daśamaikādaśau caiva sarvakāryeṣu siddhidam
lagnaṃ kanyā tulā caiva kumbhaś caiva viśeṣataḥ
- 6.30 vṛṣaś caiva samākhyātaḥ sarvakalyāṇasampradaḥ
ravir haste bhavet siddhir mṛge candras tathaiva ca

A f47v

Ω = AB(→C)

- 26a ārdra] BC; ādrā A • dhaniṣṭhā] AC; dhaniṣṭhām B
26b śatabhiṣottara] em.; śatabhiṣottarā AB; śatabhiṣottarās C
• trayah] BC; trayam A 26d smṛtāḥ] BC; smṛtā A
27a sthirārambhāḥ] BC; sthirārambhā A
28a candraṃ] AC; candra B
28c janma] C; janmaś AB
29a daśamaikādaśau] em.; daśamaikādaśās C; daśamekādaśās AB
29c lagnaṃ] AC; lagna B • tulā] BC; tulaṃ A
30b sampradaḥ] conj. Sanderson; saṃpadaḥ] BC; saṃpadaṃ A
30c ravir] A; ravi BC • siddhir] C; siddhiḥ AB
30d mṛge] BC; mṛga A • tathaiva] BC; tathaita A

- 6.31 bhaumaḥ kṛttikaśaṃyukto budhe caivānurādhakaḥ
revatī gurusāṃyuktā śukravāre punarvasuḥ
- 6.32 śaniḥ śravaṇayoge tu siddhiyogāḥ prakīrtitāḥ
ādityāṣṭamiyoge ca daśamī candrayogataḥ
- 6.33 ekādaśī śukrayuktā budhayuktā trayodaśī
ete siddhikarā yogāḥ sthirārambhāḥ prakīrtitāḥ C f23v
- 6.34 meruṃ madhye pratiṣṭhāpya sūryacandrātmakaṃ likhet
pūrvāparagatā rekhā dakṣiṇottaraḡās tathā
- 6.35 divā cakraṃ tu dakṣārdhaṃ niśā cakrottarārdhakam
aharniśivibhāgena bāhyādhyātmikayor api B f40r
- 6.36ab cakradvayaṃ pravakṣyāmi yathāvat tat tathā śṛṇu

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

31a bhaumaḥ] BC; bhauma A

32a śaniḥ] em.; śani ABC 32c ca] BC; na A

33d sthirārambhāḥ] BC; sthirārambhā A

• prakīrtitāḥ] BC; prakīrtitā A

34a meruṃ] A; meru BC

• pratiṣṭhāpya] A; pratiṣṭhā[-] C; pratiṣṭhā[-] B

35d bāhyādhyātmikayor] A; bāhyā[-]tmikayor BC

36b yathāvat tat tathā] BC; yathāvatta[-]tathā A

6.36cd dhūmāṅgāriṇi jvālā ca pūrvārdhapraharānvitā

6.37 yatra yāsyati sā dhūmā tyaktā cāṅgāriṇi matā
savitā yatra smṛtā jvālā sā śubhodayam ādiśet

6.38 udayaṃ cāśubhaṃ caiva dhūmāṅgāriṇikā dvayam
pūrvadakṣāntare caiva rekhātrayanipātanam

6.39 dakṣāpare tathā caivaṃ rekhānāṃ ca vikalpanā
udayādi samārabhya yāvad astaṃ gato raviḥ

6.40 bāhyacakravibhāgena lakṣed adhyātmikaṃ priye
jvālodayavibhāgena bāhyādhyātmikayor api

6.41 śakunais tadudbhavair vidyāt taddiśābhāgalakṣitaiḥ
prāguktaiḥ śakunair devi bāhyasthaiḥ khabhuvātmakaiḥ

6.42ab evaṃ dinavibhāgaṃ yac chubhaṃ tat parigraham

A f48f

Ω = AB(→C)

37a sā dhūmā] BC; śādhāmaṃ A

37b tyaktā] BC; tyaktvā A

37d śubhodayam C; śubhoda[[śa]]yam A; 'subhodayam B

38d nipātanam] BC; nipātitaṃ A

39a dakṣāpare] BC; dakṣāparaḥ A • caivaṃ] AB; caiva C

39c udayādi] BC; udayadi A

39d astaṃ] BC; asta A • raviḥ] AC; ravi B

40a bāhya] AB; bāhyaṃ C 40c jvālodaya] A; jvālādvaya BC

41b taddiśā] AB; tadiśā C 41c lakṣitaiḥ] AB; lakṣaṇaiḥ C

41d bāhyasthaiḥ khabhuvātmakaiḥ] C; bāhyasthaiḥkhabhuvātma[[ni]]kaiḥ B;

bāhyasthaiścabhuvātmakaiḥ A

42b parigraham] A; patigrahaṃ BC

- 6.42cd niśāyāṃ saṃpravakṣyāmi śāntā cakre yathāsthitam
6. 43 nirmālyam puṣpitaṃ caiva mukulaṃ cāpi lakṣayet
niśāmukhādim ārabhya yāvat pratyūṣagocaram
6. 44 pūrvarekhāsamaṃ kṛtvā sandhyārdhapraharānvitā
śāśicakraṃ smṛtaṃ hy evaṃ tyaktā nairmālyam ucyate
- 6.45 śāśir yatra smṛtaṃ puṣpaṃ mukulaṃ yatra yāsyati
tatkāle 'pi yathāpūrvam śakunāny upalakṣayet
- 6.46ab bāhyādhyātmikayogena śubhā grāhyā 'śubhās tyajet

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

42d sthitam] AB; sthitaḥ C

43c ārabhya] BC; āra[[sya]]bhya A

44b sandhyārdha] A; sandhyārdham BC

46a bāhyādhyātmikayogena] AC; bāhyādhyātmi[-]yogena B

6. 46cd horāvākyākṣarasthānād āyapāto 'thavā priye
- 6.47 aṣṭāraṃ cakram ālikhya dhvajādyam prastared budhaḥ
pūrve dhvajam vijānīyād dakṣiṇe siṃha ucyate
- 6.48 vṛṣaḥ paścimato jñeyo gajaś caivottare tathā
sthirāyās te samuddiṣṭāḥ śakunādyam taddiśāhitam
- 6.49 dhūmam agnau vijānīyād itisthe śvāna ucyate
tiryagge khara ity ukto mūrdhnisthe dhvāṃkṣakam viduḥ
- 6.50 taduttham śakunādyam ca calāyacayakāraḥ
aśubhārthe 'śubhā grāhyāḥ śubhārthe ca śubhā matāḥ

B f40v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 46d 'thavā] AB; yathā C
 47b dhvajādyam] C; dhavādyām AB
 47c vijānīyād] C; vijānīyāt AB
 48a vṛṣaḥ] A; vṛṣa BC • jñeyo] C; jñeyāḥ AB
 48c sthirāyās] AB; sthirāyām C
 49c tiryagge] em.; tiryage ABC
 50b calāya] AB; caloya C
 50c grāhyā{ḥ}] C; grāhyā AB
 50d matāḥ] B; matā{ḥ} C; matā A

- 6.51 samyag jñātvā tu mantrajño bhūparigrahaṃ ācāret
svābhipretasya mānasya caturthāṃśādhikaṃ khaṇet
- 6.52 samantād vistaraṃ proktaṃ nimnaṃ yāvaj jalāntikaṃ
cinmātraṃ vā khaṇet prājñāḥ puruṣārdhaṃ athāpi vā
- 6.53 ardhārdhaṃ vātha hastārdhaṃ dṛḍhā vā yatra gocare
paścād āpūrayet prājñāḥ khātaṃ ca tat samantataḥ
- 6.54 cayasyāpūraṇaṃ neṣṭaṃ pakveṣṭakamayena tu
śilāmāyo 'thavādhasatā so 'pi bhāraguruḥ smṛtaḥ
- 6.55 ubhayaṃ calate devi phaṇīndraviniivartanaīḥ
bhūkamparathayātrābhīr hastyaśvādi-paribhramaiḥ

A f48v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 51a samyag] C; samyak A; {samyak} B
51d caturthāṃśādhikaṃ] AC; caturthāsāṃdhikaṃ B • khaṇet] BC; likhet A
52c vā] AB; ca C 53b dṛḍhā] AB; dṛḍhāṃ C
53d samantataḥ] em.; samantayoḥ ABC
54b pakveṣṭaka] AB; pakṣeṣṭaka C • tu] BC; tuḥ A
54c 'thavādhasatā] A; tha[-]dhasatā BC
54d bhāra] B; bhāva A; bhāga C • guruḥ] AC; guru B
• smṛtaḥ] BC; smṛtāḥ A 55b viniivartanaīḥ] BC; viniivarttanai A
55c kampa] AB; kampaṃ C • yātrābhīr] AC; yātrābhi B
55d paribhramaiḥ] BC; paribhrameḥ A

- 6.56 tasmān neṣṭamayam kuryān na ca pāṣāṇasaṃcayaḥ
mṛdā vā kevalam noktaṃ na dṛḍham sphāṭanam bhavet
6. 57 hastāpūrāśmaprastārair mṛdam aṣṭāṅgulocchrayam
sekaṃ caivodakaṃ kṛtvā koṭṭanam ca prati prati
- 6.58 palāśāśvatthakādyaiś ca hastipādakṛtena tu
adho vipulakaṃ taṃ tu nābhimātroccchrayeṇa tu
- 6.59 grāhe hrāsam prakartavyam grahordhve vṛttamastakam
yathāśaktyā hataṃ kṛtvā prastāraikaṃ punaḥ prati
- 6.60 anenāpūrayet khātaṃ pādūnaṃ yāvad āgatam
prāsādamānataś caiva upariṣṭād vāstukaḥpanā

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

56c calaṃ] B; balaṃ AC

57c caivodakaṃ] A; caivo[-]kaṃ B; caive[-]kaṃ C

58b tu] BC; tuḥ A

59d prati] C; pratiḥ AB

60d upariṣṭād] AC; upaviṣṭād B

- 6.61 saśalyā vā viśalyā vā vikṛtā śakunena vā
manasā kalpayitvā tu vāstau śalyān nirūpayet
- 6.62 purā coddhāraḥ vakṣye vāstusūtre yathā sthitam
taduddhṛtya samāṃ kṛtvā vāstusūtraṃ prasārayet
- 6.63 vakṣyamāṇavidhānena prakrāntaṃ caiva vakṣyate
pratiṣṭhālakṣaṇaṃ caiva pādākhyasya ca suvrate
- 6.64 samā kṣmā tatpramāṇā yā tatrāhṛtya śilāṣṭakam
kumbhāṣṭāv agnikuṇḍāṣṭau caikaṃ vā nipuṇo guruḥ
- 6.65 yajed vāstunaraṃ tatra vakṣyamāṇayathāhitam
gandhapuṣpādibhir divyair balibhiḥ sārvaśikāḥ

C f24r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 61a saśalyā] BC; śasalyā A
61d śalyān] AC; śalyā B
62d sūtraṃ] AC; sūtra B
63b prakrāntaṃ] AC; prakrānta B
• vakṣyate] BC; lakṣyate A
64a kṣmā] AB; [-] C
65c divyair] AC; divyaiḥ B

- 6.66 tadūrdhve tu yajec chaktiṃ sarvādhvānavidhāriṇīm
śaktyūrdhve tu nyased vedīr vasusaṃkhyā diśāṣṭasu
- 6.67 navamī madhyadeśe tu huhūkaṃ tatra vinyaset
tadūrdhve vinyaset brahmaśilāṃ śaktiṃ ca śāmbhavīm
- 6.68 tasyāṃ rudrāṣṭakaṃ sarvaṃ mūrtyādisahitaṃ nyaset
dhāturatnauṣadhīlohabījapāradagarbhitān
- 6.69 nyastān antasureśādīn rukmatārāruṇodbhavān
kalaśān vinyasec chaktau tanmantrair madhyapūrvakān
- 6.70 tadūrdhvaṃ vinyaset proktā vedīr lokeśvarāṇubhiḥ
hastmātrās tu vedāśrās ṭṭīyāṃśasamucchrayāḥ

B f41r

A f49r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

66c ūrdhve] AB; ārdhe C • nyased] BC; nyaset A

66d vedīr] em.; vedī AB; vedīṃ C

67c ūrdhve] A; ūrdhvaṃ C; ūrddhva B

67d śilāṃ] C; śilā AB

69a sureśādīn] BC; sureśādī A

69b rukma] B; rūkma C; kragma A

69c kalaśān] em.; kalasān A; kalamāsān BC

• vinyasec] A; vinyaset C; vinyase B • chaktau] A; śaktau BC

69d mantrair] BC; maṃtrai A

70a proktā] BC; prājño A 70b vedīr] em.; vedī A; vedi BC

• lokeśvarāṇubhiḥ] C; lokeśvarāṇubhiḥ A; lokeśvarāṇubhiḥ B

70d ṭṭīyāṃśa] AC; ṭṭīyāśaṃ B

- 6.71 lokapālāyudhāṅkā vā padmāṣṭadalabhūṣitāḥ
śivamantram lavarṇastham uccārya navamīm nyaset
- 6.72 adhobhuvanam etaṃ tu kālākhyasya ca suvrate
ṣaḍāvaraṇaparyantaṃ kālākhyādiprakīrtitam
- 6.73 kālordhvam ātmatattvaṃ syāt tanmātrāntaṃ tu vidyayā
buddhikarmendriyopetaṃ mano 'ntaṃ vyāptim iṣyate
- 6.74 guṇatrayakṛtātopaṃ garvabuddhisamanvitam
śivākhyam evam adhvānaṃ pādanyāse prakalpayet
- 6.75ab mūle madhye tathordhve ca kalpyaṃ tattvatrayaṃ tridhā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 71d navamīm] AC; navamī B
72a bhuvanam] BC; bhuvanaṃ A
72b kālākhyasya] BC; kālākhyam A
72d kālākhyādi] BC; kā[-]khyādi A
73b vidyayā AC; vidyathā B
73c karmendriyopetaṃ] AC; karmendriy[-]etaṃ B
73d mano 'ntaṃ] conj.; manottaṃ AB; manoktaṃ C
75b kalpyaṃ] AB; kalpāṃ C

- 6.75cd kalpayitvā tato 'dhīśān brahmaviṣṇuharān kramāt
- 6.76 dharmam jñānam ca vairāgyam aiśvaryaṃ ca caturthakam
āgneyādikrameṇaiva yāvad īśānagocare
- 6.77 pādarūpāḥ smṛtā hy ete harirūpeṇa cāmunā
adharmājñānakam caiva avairāgyam anaiśvaram
- 6.78 gātrakāś caturo hy ete pūrvādyāś cottarāntagāḥ
sthiram enaṃ sadādhvānam ābrahmabhuvanāntikam
- 6.79 tatra puṣpaiḥ prakalpyādau nirodhya vinyaset punaḥ
rudrāṣṭakam tu vidhivan mūrtyaṣṭakasamanvitam
- 6.80 gandhapuṣpādibhir bhadre pūjayec ca śilāṣṭake
kṣamāṃ pūrve tu vinyasya āgneyyām agnim eva ca

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

76c āgneyādi] AC; agneyādi B

• krameṇaiva] BC; kramenaiva A

77a rūpāḥ] C; rūpā A

78a gātrakāś] AC; gātrakā B

78c sadādhvānam] B; sadādhyānam C; madādhvānam A

78d ābrahma] AC; abrahma B

79a puṣpaiḥ prakalpyādau] A; puṣpairprakalpyādau B; puṣpai[-]kalpyādau C

79c vidhivan] C; vidhivat AB

80b śilāṣṭake] BA; śivāṣṭakam A

80d āgneyyām] B; āgneyyam C; agneyyām A

6.81 yāmyadig yajamānaṃ tu nairṛte kaṃ nyased budhaḥ
vāruṇe varuṇaṃ nyasya vāyavyāṃ tiryaggaṃ nyaset

6.82 saumye indum suvinyasya aiśānyāṃ vyomakaṃ nyaset
śivamūrtiṃ nyasen madhye prāsādānte ca vyomagāṃ

B f41v

6.83 mūrtinyāse kṛte paścād ato nyāstv adhidevatāḥ
śarvaḥ paśupatiś cogro rudro bhavas tathaiva ca

A f49v

6.84 īśānaś ca mahādevo bhīmo mūrtyadhidevatāḥ
indrāgniś ca yamaś caiva rakṣeśo varuṇas tathā

6.85 vāyuḥ somas tathēśānaḥ pūrvādīśāntagocare
kumbhāṣṭakeṣu nyastavyā lokapālāstrasaṃyutāḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

81b nairṛte] em.; nairṛter ABC

• nyased] AC; nyaset B

81c varuṇaṃ] BC; vāruṇaṃ A

81d tiryaggaṃ] em.; tiryagaṃ ABC

82a indum] AC; indu B

• suvinyasya] A; [-]vinyasya BC

82d vyomagāṃ] AC; vyomagāṃ A

83b nyāstv adhidevatāḥ; AB; nyāsthādhidevatāḥ C

83d rudro bhavas] AB; [— —]vas C

85b pūrvādīśānta] A; pūrvādīśānta BC

- 6.86 svanāmamantrās teṣāṃ hi praṇavādinamontikāḥ
pūjākāle prakartavyāḥ svāhāntā homakarmaṇi
- 6.87 sṛṣṭyā tattvādivinyāsaṃ saṃśuddhiḥ saṃhṛtikramāt
saṃpūjyaivaṃ vidhānais tu balidhūpasurāsavaḥ
- 6.88 sāṅgaṃ kuṇḍeṣu saṃpūjya samittilaghṛtādibhiḥ
svāgnau homaṃ prakartavyaṃ jñātvā dravyabalābalaṃ
- 6.89 mūrtimūrtyādhipānāṃ tu lokapālāṃ tathaiva ca
śataṃ vāpi sahasraṃ vā tasyāpy ardhamaṃ athāpi vā
- 6.90 svatattvādhvavibhāgena yathākāmaṃ viśodhayet
śīlasamīpato gatvā śiktvā śaktighaṭāmbhasā

C f24v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 86c prakartavyāḥ] em.; prakartavyā] ABC
87a vinyāsaṃ] C; vinyāsa AB
87b saṃśuddhiḥ] em.; saṃśuddhis ABC
87c vidhānais] BC; vidhānes A
88c prakartavyaṃ] AC; prakartavya B
90b yathākāmaṃ] A; yath[-]maṃ C; yathā[-]maṃ B
90d śiktvā] AB; śikhā C
• śakti] C; śanti AB

- 6.91 śilāṃ saṃspr̥śya darbheṇa digīśān pūjayed guruḥ
tattvatrayaṃ ca vinyasya japtvā hutvā ca śaktitaḥ
- 6.92 bhāge bhāge tataḥ kuryāt sandhānaṃ tattvayoḥ kramāt
śuddhāśuddhātmano devi hrasvadīrghoktasasvaraiḥ
- 6.93 nirvartyaivaṃ tato varjyaṃ marma vāstor niveśayet
dhruvayoge sunakṣatre karaṇe vārasaṃyute
- 6.94 kartuś cāpy anukūle vā śilāsthāpanam ārabhet
supratiṣṭhajagārambhakāladyānātmavṛttinā
- 6.95 saptāhutīr dadet paścād dhyātvā tadguṇasaṃyutāḥ
anena vidhiyogena guruṇā saṃniveśitam

A f50r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 91a śilāṃ] AC; śilā B
- 91b pūjayed] C; pūjayet AB
- 92b sandhānaṃ] em.; sandhāna A; satvānaṃ B; sahvānaṃ C
- kramāt] BC; kramāṭḥ A
- 92d dīrghoktasasvaraiḥ] AC; dīrghoktamasvaraiḥ B
- 93a nirvartyaivaṃ] em.; nirvartyaiva BC; nivartyaivaṃ A
- varjyaṃ] C; varjya AB
- 93b vāstor] A; vāsto B; vāstā C
- 93c sunakṣatre] A; sunakṣatra C; sanakṣatre B
- 93d karaṇe] BC; karaṇai A
- saṃyute] BC; saṃyutaḥ A
- 94c jagārambha] AB; jagārambhe C
- 95a saptāhutīr] C; saptāhutī AB
- 95b guṇasaṃyutāḥ] em.; guṇasaṃyutā] A; guṇamayutāḥ BC

6.96 yathābhipretasaṃsiddhis tathā bhavati nānyathā
tasyordhve kalpayitvā tu adhvānaṃ vakṣyamāṇakam

6.97 prāsādātmagataṃ caiva prakṛtādyam śivāntikam
tattvasaṃdhānakam caiva kalpayec cādhidaivatam

B f42r

6.98 tato bhūtagaṇebhyaś ca baliṃ vai sārvaśāntikam
sarvānnasahitaṃ dadyāt svamantrakṛtavigrahaḥ

6.99 praṇavaṃ ca diśāṃ śabdaṃ vāsibhyaś ca tataḥ param
aghorebhyo 'tha ghorebhyo ghoraghoratarebhyaś ca

6.100 sarvataḥ sarvasarvebhyo namaḥ sarvātmaneti ca
'bhyontaśabdatraṇam datvā bhūtamāṭṛdiśādhipān

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

96d adhvānaṃ] AB; ādhānaṃ C

• vakṣyamāṇakam] C; vakṣyamāṇanakaṃ B; vakṣyamānakam A

97a prāsādātmagataṃ] BC; prāsādātma[[ta]]gataṃ A

97c tattva] BC; [[tva]]tatva A

98a gaṇebhyaś] BC; gaṇābhyaś A

98b sārva] BC; sarva A

99a śabdaṃ] BC; sarvaṃ A

98b vāsibhyaś] A; vāsibhyeś B; vāsinyaś C

100a sarvasarvebhyo] AC; sarvaḥsarvebhyo B

100b sarvātmaneti ca] C; sarvātmanetica[[sarva]] A; savātmanetica B

- 6.101 namaś cānte prayoktavyaṃ pūjākāle vipaścitā
dhūpe svāhā prayoktavyā svadhākārārghadāpane
- 6.102 vaṣaḍantaṃ dadet pānaṃ vaṣaḍantā balikriyā
hūṃ visarjya tatopāyāt phaṭkārāstrasammucaran
- 6.103 evaṃ sarvatra dātavyas tatsthāne tu diśābaliḥ
svaśāstre vihitaṃ vātha balikarmādim ācaret
- 6.104 svanāmamantribhir jñātvā graharakṣāṃ pradāpayet
datvā balim śubhāvāptir bhavet prāsādakalpanā
- 6.105 anyathā tu mahāvighnaṃ prakurvanti vināyakāḥ
tasmāt sarvatra dātavyo balir vai sārvaśāstrikāḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 102a pānaṃ] BC; paścāt A
102d samuccaran] AB; samuccaret C
103b baliḥ] conj.; balim] ABC
104a mantribhir] AC; mantribhiḥ B
104b graharakṣāṃ] C; graharakṣā B; grahaṃrakṣāṃ A
105b prakurvanti] BC; praku[[rvva]]rvvanti A
105c sarvatra] AB; sarvaḥ C

6.106 ihāmutra phalair yogaḥ samāptārambhakarmasu
tat kṛtātmā samācamya datvā vai śivadakṣiṇām

6.107ab śivam astv ity anujñāto vibhoḥ prāsādam ārabhet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

106b karmasu] BC; karmasuḥ A

106c kṛtātmā] BC; kṛtvātmā A

106d dakṣiṇām] C; dakṣiṇāṃ A; dakṣiṇā B

107a anujñāto] AC; anujñātoḥ B